

Paper 26

RESEARCH ON IMPACT OF DEMONETIZATION

Fairooz v. p.*, Chandini k.*

*Srinivasa Institute of Management Studies Pandeshwar

ABSTRACT

The move by the government to demonetize RS 500 and RS 1000 notes by replacing them with new RS 500 and RS 2000 notes has taken the country with surprise .The move by the Indian government is to tackle the menace of black money ,corruption, terror funding and fake money. This case study shows Demonetization is making people to suffer a lot .some agrees that strategy of demonetization is good but its execution is so poor. It is very difficult for common people. But demonetization have got a long term strategy which are yet in progress. Presently we Indians are struggling but in future it may help in developing our economy. Demonetization help government in various ways such as helps in increasing government revenue, decrease the fiscal deficit, control corruption, controls fake money, control terror funding and also tracking people who have large amount of unaccounted cash. People are facing lots of problem due to demonetization but it may only for short period. It is quite good for our economy but it is difficult for common people to get the normal money and there is no balance or change available in the market it is also affecting the daily wage workers and also the purchasing power have decreased .Demonetization is positive long term benefits with small negative impact. It helps tracking or chasing people who have been involved in illegal activities on other hand it creates a lot of chaos for those people who is not involved in any illegal activities. It encourages digitalized Indian economy and helps in developing our Indian economy. The government claim that the demonetization was an effort to stop counterfeiting of the current banknotes allegedly used for funding terrorism, as well as a crackdown on black money in the country. The move also described as an effort to reduce corruption, the use of drugs and also smuggling. In current our Indian economy is recovering its negative impact that had on past time of demonetization.

Keywords : Demonetization, black money, terror funding, long term benefits, economy.

INTRODUCTION

Meaning

Demonetization refers to Withdrawal of a particular form of currency from circulation. Demonetization is necessary whenever there is a change of national currency. The old unit of

currency must be removed and substituted with a new currency unit. The currency was demonetized first time in 1946 and second time in 1978. On Nov. 2016 the currency is demonetized third time by the present Modi government. This is the bold step taken by the govt. for the betterment of the economy and country.

Demonetization is the act of stripping a currency unit of its status as legal tender. It occurs whenever there is a change of national currency: The current form or forms of money is pulled from circulation and retired, often to be replaced with new notes or coins. India has demonetized before: First time on 12 Jan 1946 (Saturday), second time on 16 Jan 1978 (Monday), Third time on 8th November 2016 (Tuesday).

History of demonetization

The first currency ban:

In 1946, the currency note of Rs 1,000 and Rs 10,000 were removed from circulation. The ban really did not have much impact, as the currency of such higher denomination was not accessible to the common people. However, both the notes were reintroduced in 1954 with an additional introduction of Rs 5,000 currency. Rs 500 and Rs 1000 notes were introduced in 1934 and after four years in 1938, Rs 10,000 notes were introduced.

The second currency ban:

This came in 1978, the then Prime Minister of India Morarji Desai announced the currency ban taking Rs 1000, Rs 5000 and Rs 10,000 out of circulation. The sole aim of the ban was to curb black money generation in the country.

The French were the first to use the word Demonetize, in the years between 1850 -1855. Since then many countries have used the word and the policy with immense restriction and discomfort, for it disrupts economics and population at large.

Other countries which adopted demonetization are the following:-

1) Ghana

In 1982, Ghana rolled out the decision to demonetize their 50 cedi currency notes in order to monitor money laundering and corruption. The change was not welcomed warmly, creating chaos across the country and finally resulted in a move back to physical assets and foreign currency.

2) Nigeria

Nigeria's economy collapsed after the 1984 demonetization move that did not go as planned. The military government of then President Muhammadu Buhari introduced different coloured notes to invalidate their old currency in order to fight black money

3) Myanmar

Around 80% of Myanmar's currency was demonetized in 1987 by the military to curb black money, but the move resulted in a lot of protests and the country witnessed several killings.

4) Soviet Union

Under the governance of Mikhail Gorbachev in 1991, the then Soviet Union demonetized the higher denominations of ruble bills, the 50s and 100s. The move did not go well and resulted in takeover of Mikhail's leadership within eight months of the plan.

5) North Korea

North Korea faced demonetization of their currency in 2010, which led to major economy breakdown with people left to starve for basics.

6) Zimbabwe

Zimbabwe once had hundred trillion dollar note, which was demonetized and was exchanged in a mocking way dropping trillion dollars to \$0.5 dollar.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- ✓ To know how demonetization affected common people.
- ✓ To know how demonetization help in developing our economy.
- ✓ Identifying the positive and negative impact of demonetization.
- ✓ To understand the long term as well as short term result of demonetization.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The impact of demonetization is leading to riot like situation in the country. It is demand that common people have immediate access to enough money to pay for their daily needs and health emergencies .The role of government is to undertake honest tax administration and not to threat the common people to stand in line and filling forms to access their own legitimate money. Demonetization is a bold decision taken by government for curbing all black money in India.Major aim of demonetization is making India a cash less society. There is a huge impact on demonetization in India. Due to demonetization a lot of people are suffering and thus government are not answerable for certain questions of public. Thus this demonetization will help us to become digitalized India.

The main reason for demonetizing are the following:-

Removing Black Money from Country

Stopping Of Corruption

Terror funding

Curbing Fake Note

Stopping Illegal Dabba Trading

To Send a Clear Message That This Government Is Well Inclined Towards Working for the Development of Nation

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research methodology is a way to systematically solve the research problem. Research methods may be understood as all those methods or techniques that are used for conducting research .Research process includes formulating the research problem, extensive literature survey, preparing the research ,determining the sample design, collecting the data,excecution of data ,generalization and interpretation and preparation of the project on this basis.

The research was based on study of a sample, sized 150, using simple random sample and also with the help of secondary data .The research included collection of data from the primary sources using the research tool (questionnaire).Final stage was to analyze, interpret and draw conclusions from the data collected.

Data Sources:

Primary Data

Primary data collected from respondents using questionnaire by online.

Secondary Data

Secondary data are collected from websites and various books.

Research approach

Descriptive approach

Research Instruments used for Data collection

Both primary and secondary data are used to study. In this study, primary data are generated from online survey with respondents through questionnaire .For this study, main source of secondary data are from websites. Both internal and external sources are used in this study.

Data was collected through the use self-administered questionnaires.The questionnaire was divided into two sections. The first section consisted of demographic indices that collected information on the respondent's demography. The second section consisted of the other indicators derived from the literature whose availability is and functionalities in organizations are measured.

In the data collection procedure the questionnaire were distributed to 150 participants. The participants were instructed to answer the questions posed in the questionnaire to the best of their knowledge. All 150 questionnaire administered were returned, but only 139 were found to be fully completed and thus usable, representing a response rate of 88.23 percent. This response rate was considered a success .In this study the participants were assured of the protection of their identities and also the confidentiality of their responses to the questions posed in the questionnaire.

Limitation of the study

- Limited time for this study.
- People are not responding to the questionnaire.
- Hence demonetization have got long term benefits collected data may differ from time.

Demonetization have positive impact mainly on:-

Table 1

Positive impact	percentage
It helps in removing black money	47.3%
Removing terror funding	3%
Moving towards digital payments	8.5%
Helps in increasing tax revenue	2.4%
Above all	38.8%

Figure 1

Interpretation

In the above graph, it is shown the positive impact that have on demonetization. It is clear from the graph the main positive impact of demonetization it is helps in removing black money and 38.8% shows that demonetization have positive impact mainly on removing terror funding, moving towards digital payment, helps in increasing tax revenue and also removes black money.

Demonetization affect common people

Table 2

opinions	Percentage
Standing queue for long period	47.7%
No change in shops	14.1%
Not getting enough money	25%
Not able to purchase livelihood	13.3%

Figure 2

Interpretation

The above pie chart shows how demonetization affecting common people. It shows 48% of common people are suffering by standing in queue for long period, 25% are not getting enough money, 14% are not getting change from shops and 13% are not able to purchase their livelihood.

The people are suffering due to demonetization

Table 3

Opinions	percentage
YES	82%
NO	18%

Figure 3

Interpretation

In the above chart shows the result whether the people are suffering due to demonetization .82% shows the people are suffering due to demonetization and 18% shows the people are not suffering due to demonetization.

Demonetization is controlling black money and corruption

Table 4

Opinions	percentage
Track people who are having large sum of unaccounted cash	48.4%

Political parties in crisis a head of enforcement and income	6.3%
Controls fake money	25.4%
Decrease in illegal activities	19.8%

Figure 4

Interpretation

The above chart shows how demonetization helps in controlling black money and corruption in our economy. According to the graph it shows 48.4% helps in tracking people who are having large sum of unaccounted cash, 25.4% helps in controlling fake money, 19.8% helps in decrease in illegal activities and 63% controls political parties ahead of enforcement and income.

Demonetization helps in developing our Indian economy

Table 5

Developing the economy	Percentage
Helps in increasing government revenue	28.3%

Decrease the fiscal deficit	10.2%
Control corruption	39.4%
India will be digitalized	22%

Figure 5

Interpretation

In the above graph 39.4% shows demonetization helps in controlling corruption ,28.3%helps in increasing government tax revenue,22%shows that India will be digitalized and 10.2% shows demonetization decrease the fiscal deficit.

CONCLUSION

This study provides valuable implications regarding the impact of demonetization undertaken by the government as a large shock to the economy. The impact of the shock in the medium term is a function of how much of the currency will be replaced at the end of the replacement process and the extent to which currency in circulation is extinguished. While it has been argued that the cash that would be extinguished would be “black money” and hence, should be rightfully extinguished to set right the perverse incentive structure in the economy, this argument is based on impressions rather than on facts. While the facts are not available to anybody, it would be foolhardy to argue that this is the only possibility. As argued above, it is possible that these cash balances were used as a medium of exchange. In other words, while the cash was mediating in legitimate economic activity, if this currency is extinguished there

would be a contraction of economic activity in the economy and that is a cost that needs to be factored in while assessing the impact of the demonetization on the economy and its agents. It is likely that there would be a spurt in the banking deposits. While interpreting the phenomenon, however, one has to keep in mind that a large part of their deposits were earlier used for transactional purposes.

REFERENCES

Dhananjay Mahapatra (Nov 16, 2016) Objective behind note ban laudable, says supreme court, Times of India

www.wikipedia.com

www.google.com

Braga, F.D., Isabella G and Mazzon J.A., (2013). Digital wallets as a payment method influence consumer in their buying behavior

PTI. (2016, Nov. 9). Demonetisation will benefit economy in long run: Jaitley. The Hindu Business Line.